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MED-GOLD

Turning climate-related information into added value for traditional **MED**iterranean **G**rape, **OL**ive and **D**urum wheat food systems

Deliverable 3.3

Report on the climatic, bioclimatic and extreme climate indices developed in the wine pilot services

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

In this deliverable, we report the main results obtained to provide scientific robustness to the information included in the MED-GOLD wine service with particular attention devoted to the different indicators of interest for the wine sector shown in the visualization interface developed: the MED-GOLD Dashboard.

In this perspective, the overall structure of this work follows the tripartition of the MED-GOLD Dashboard: historical climate, seasonal forecast, and climate projections.

This work will assure users that the key climate-related information that the MED-GOLD wine service makes available for the decision making process of the industrial users rely upon a robust and well established scientific background, authoritative, up-to-date and easily further improved in the future.

Additionally, some additional insights on possible future improvements will be presented here in terms of novel approach (the UNSEEN method) and in terms of satellite data exploitation.

In order to reconstruct and monitor the observed climate, from the analysis of the main climatological features represented by the gridded datasets used in the MED-GOLD Dashboard (i.e. PTHRES, ERA5) it can be clearly observed that the climate for the reference period 1981-2010 with respect to 1951-1980 over the region of interest for the MED-GOLD wine service is generally warmer. This leads to a general reduction of the risk of the need of additional sanitary treatments and an increase of possible heat stress for the grapes.

Looking at the two main gridded datasets present in the MED-GOLD Dashboard, some main results can be highlighted: Firstly, the representations of the climatological average of the indicators of interest for the MED-GOLD wine service for the present climate look quite similar, while some discrepancies can be pointed out for the past climate. However, the high-resolution dataset PTHRES exhibits some local patterns not present (or, if present, weaker) in the 30-km reanalysis system dataset (ERA5). Moreover, a critical role can be played by the spatial resolution of datasets when extreme indicators with a fixed temperature threshold have been taken into exam and, in general, in the representation of interannual temperature variability. The above results lead to some consequent discrepancies in the representation of the MED-GOLD compound risk indexes (e.g higher mean risk of heat stress in PTHRES, different spatial distribution of interannual variability of sanitary risk).

Looking at different sources of information for monitoring the present climate, the exploitation of the open Copernicus program and the Landsat program can provide information near real time, which compared with climate and bioclimatic data, can indicate how could be the behaviour of a crop under a hypothetical climate condition in the near future. The indices based on remote sensing closely follow the periodicity associated with variations in phenology (NDVI) and climate variations (NDWI, LST, NMDI).

The quality assessment of seasonal predictions for ECVs, bioclimatic indicators and compound risk indexes over the Iberian Peninsula and the Douro valley (Portugal) shows the bias-adjustment allows a close reproduction of the observed climatology in all the predicted ECVs and bioclimatic indicators. In the case of ECVs, temperature usually gives better skill than precipitation. Regarding the bioclimatic indicators, the skill depends on its nature. In general, the more extreme an indicator, the more difficult to forecast it. Particularly, indices derived from mean temperature display the best quality. Considering a blending experiment, where observations and predictions are merged as the growing season progresses, there is an increase in skill as we enter the season and more observations are included in the indicator. This is an interesting feature because it allows the user to optimize the moment to make a decision (the best trade-off between anticipation and expected quality). Finally, the compound risk indexes show some

potential in the Douro region, specially in the inner / northern Douro and some specific start dates (i.e. June for the Heat Index and April and May, for the Sanitary Index).

Moving to longer time scales, the analysis of the climate projections reported in the MED-GOLD Dashboard revealed robust increasing changes between both the near and the distant future compared to the reference period for the temperature related indices under both RCP scenarios. On the contrary, the changes in the precipitation related indices were found less pronounced for the near future period under both RCP4.5 and RCP8.5, while the highest and more robust decreases were identified for the distant future period under RCP8.5.

Finally, The UNSEEN (UNprecedented Simulated Extremes using ENsembles) method was used to assess the risk of unprecedented rainfall events over the wine-growing regions of northern Portugal. Following this approach, a large ensemble of initialised climate model simulations was analysed, and the probability of unprecedented rainfall in each season was quantified. Seasonal rainfall totals considerably higher than any observed are possible in the current climate. The probability of an event in either season is low (0.02), and the chance of reoccurrence of a year similar to 1993, when both seasons were exceptionally wet, is extremely small. The results help inform the need for costly adaptation investments for vineyard management, such as better availability of spraying machinery and labour, high-gauge drainage, landslide controls or even abandonment of exposed vineyard areas.

The main results of this work will provide relevant material that can be included in future scientific publications. Moreover, methods that can further improve the MED-GOLD services (eg. MED-GOLD Dashboard) by adding new contents even after the end of the project to go closer to the market in terms of new source of info (satellite) and innovative approach (e.g. UNSEEN) have been presented here. The main scientific contents of this work can ultimately further favour the commercial exploitation of the MED-GOLD Services by demonstrating the scientific consistency of the information provided to users.

Moreover, the lessons learnt on the climatic, bioclimatic and extreme climate indices developed in the wine pilot service (for instance on the relevance of going to higher spatial resolution, on the adoption of datasets already known by users and on the merging of observation and climate predictions to increase the skills of forecast...) can pave the way to support a replication process for other crops and over different areas.

1. OBJECTIVES

The main objectives of this deliverable are here summarised:

- Show the main results on climatic, bioclimatic and extreme climate indices developed and adopted in the wine pilot service.
- Assess scientific robustness and authoritativeness of the main results reported in the MED-GOLD dashboard.
- Report the back-end work done for the climate predictions on downscaling, bias correction, and comparison between different sources of data in order to provide authoritative and certified climate information in the wine service
- Present some insights on the possible new approaches that can further improve the MED-GOLD wine service even after the end of the project in terms of a new approach (the UNSEEN method) and in terms of exploitation of satellite data
- Support the future process of replication of the service

With this deliverable, the project has contributed to the achievement of the following objectives (DOA, PartB Table1.1):

No.	Objective	Yes
1	To co-design, co-develop, test, and assess the added value of proof-of-concept climate services for olive, grape, and durum wheat	X
2	To refine, validate, and upscale the three pilot services with the wider European and global user communities for olive, grape, and durum wheat	X
3	To ensure replicability of MED-GOLD climate services in other crops/climates (e.g., coffee) and to establish links to policy making globally	X
4	To implement a comprehensive communication and commercialization plan for MED-GOLD climate services to enhance market uptake	
5	To build better informed and connected end-user communities for the global olive oil, wine, and pasta food systems and related policy making	

2. IMPACT

This deliverable will assure users that the key climate-related information that the MED-GOLD wine service makes available for the decision-making process of the industrial users rely upon a robust and well established scientific background, authoritative, up-to-date and easily further improved in the future.

Moreover, this work will demonstrate that the workflow adopted in the service for the provision of the information they need is certified, replicable and well documented.

No.	Expected impact	Yes
1	Providing added-value for the decision-making process addressed by the project, in terms of effectiveness, value creation, optimised opportunities and minimised risk	X
2	Enhancing the potential for market uptake of climate services demonstrated by addressing the added value	
3	Ensuring the replicability of the methodological frameworks for value added climate services in potential end-user markets	
4	To implement a comprehensive communication and commercialization plan for MED-GOLD climate services to enhance market uptake	
5	To build better informed and connected end-user communities for the global olive oil, wine, and pasta food systems and related policy making	

3. DEFINITIONS

Concepts and terms used in this document and needing a definition are included in the following table:

Concept / Term	Definition
Climate projections	Probabilistic estimates of the evolution of the climate in the future, from decades up to the end of the century.
Indicator	A parameter describing a reality, i.e., synthesizing the effects of climate with relevance to a specific sector and business
Percentile	Division of the population distribution in 100 categories
Reanalysis	A method similar to analysis, but performed in real time, and the background field is created by a numerical weather prediction model that does not change over the entire period of the reanalysis.
Seasonal forecasts	Predictions of the climatic conditions for the coming months
(Predictive) Skill	A statistical measure of the accuracy of seasonal forecasts
Tercile	Division of the population distribution into three categories

Additional definitions of further terms can be found in the Concepts and terms used in <https://www.med-gold.eu/glossary/>

4. ACRONYMS

Acronyms used in this document and needing a definition are included in the following table:

Acronym	Definition
CDS-C3S	Climate Data Store - Copernicus Climate Change Service
ECV(s)	Essential Climate Variable(s)
ERA5 BE	ECMWF Atmospheric ReAnalysis 5 Back Extension 1950-1978
FRPSS	Fair Ranked Probability Skill Score
GDD	Growing Degrees Days
GST	Growing Season average Temperature
HarvestR	Harvest total precipitation
IPMA	Instituto Português do Mar e da Atmosfera
LST	Land Surface Temperature
NDVI	Normalized Difference Vegetation Index: (indicator of the greenness of the biomes)
NDWI	Normalized Difference Water Index - water monitoring index of the land surface
NMDI	Normalized Multi-band Drought Index (sensitivity to drought severity)
PTHRES	PorTugal High RESolution data set
SprR	Spring total precipitation
STD	Standard Deviation
SU35	Number of heat stress days (days with mean temp >35°C)
TVX	Temperature Vegetation Index (ratio of NDVI and LST)
UNSEEN	UNprecedented Simulated Extremes using ENsembles
WSDI	Warm Spell Duration Index

5. REFERENCES

The following documents, although not part of this document, amplify or clarify its contents. Reference documents are those not applicable and referenced within this document. They are referenced in this document in the form [RD.x]:

Ref.	Title	Code	Version	Date
[RD.1]	MED-GOLD Deliverable 3.2: Report on the methodology followed to implement the wine pilot services			2020
[RD.2]	MED-GOLD Deliverable 3.6: First feedback report from users on wine pilot service development			2019
[RD.3]	MED-GOLD Deliverable 1.3: Assessment of quality of European climate observations and their appropriateness for use in climate services for each sector			2019
[RD.4]	MED-GOLD Deliverable 3.7: Second Feedback report from users on wine pilot service development			2020
[RD.5]	MED-GOLD Deliverable 3.1: Report on the two case studies at seasonal- and long-term timescales for the wine sector			2019
[RD.6]	MED-GOLD Deliverable 1.4: Report assessing the quality of seasonal forecast information and climate projections, and their appropriateness for use in climate services for each sector:			2019
[RD.7]	Research paper: Varotsos KV, Karali A, Lemesios G, Kitsara G, Moriondo M, Dibari C, Leolini L, Giannakopoulos C (2021) Near future climate change projections with implications for the agricultural sector of three major Mediterranean islands Regional Environmental Change 21:16 doi:10.1007/s10113-020-01736-0			2021

6. DETAILED REPORT

6.1. STATE OF THE ART

The bioclimatic indicators related to vine growth , grape yields and harvest dates have been identified by the champion SOGRAPE since the early stages of the project (see [RD.2] and references therein).

The capabilities of different gridded datasets (including reanalysis systems) in reproducing the main features of the climate variables of interest, including few derived indices, for the wine service, as reported by the weather stations operated by SOGRAPE in their own vineyards and by IPMA in the Douro Valley, have been already reported in [RD.3].

Finally, the main characteristics of the climate predictions from seasonal to longer time-scales (future climate projection) over the main areas of interest for the MED-GOLD wine service in terms of skills and uncertainty associated to the key climatic variables (temperature and precipitation), as well as other few derived indices, have been reported in [RD.6].

6.2 METHODS and DATASETS

The Methodology and the datasets adopted in this report have been described in depth and fully reported in [RD.1] and [RD.3], respectively. Based on this methodological background, this Deliverable is more focused on the results obtained regarding the bio-climatic indicators of interest for the wine sector by applying the above cited methodologies.

In addition to what was reported in the previous deliverables, a new release of a gridded observational reanalysis system dataset has been taken here into account as a useful source of information for reconstructing the climate of the past: the ERA5 Back Extension (BE) 1950-1978.

6.2.1 ERA5 BACK EXTENSION (BE)

The preliminary version of the ERA5 reanalysis Back Extension (BE) from 1950 to 1978 has been recently released by C3S (November 2020). From preliminary analysis, the quality of this dataset is quite satisfactory: only some problems seem to be present in the representation of tropical cyclones that are sometimes unrealistically intense. However, this dataset can be quite useful from the MED-GOLD perspective as it can provide a long and possibly homogeneous (with respect to the near real-time ERA5 products already considered in the ongoing MED-GOLD activities) reference climatological dataset for the areas of interest of MED-GOLD services

More details on ERA5-BE can be found in

<https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/cdsapp#!/dataset/reanalysis-era5-single-levels-preliminary-back-extension?tab=overview>

6.3 MAIN RESULTS

In this section we report the main results obtained to provide scientific robustness to the information provided in the MED-GOLD Wine service and in particular to the information reported in the visualization interface developed: the MED-GOLD Dashboard. In this perspective, the overall structure of this section follows the tripartition of the MED-GOLD Dashboard: historical climate, seasonal forecast, climate projections.

Furthermore, some additional insights on possible future improvements will be presented here in terms of satellite data exploitation and in terms of a possible and promising novel approach (the UNSEEN method) to be adopted.

6.3.1 MONITORING AND RECONSTRUCTING THE OBSERVED PAST AND PRESENT CLIMATE OVER THE AREA OF INTEREST FOR THE MED-GOLD WINE SERVICE

In this section the main climatological features of interest for the MED-GOLD wine service that can be inferred for the reconstruction of the past and present climate from the two gridded observational datasets adopted in the MED-GOLD Dashboard are presented.

Moreover, some examples of possible use of Copernicus Satellite data are described, by reporting information on the evolution, development and almost real-time status of plants to be used as ancillary information, and that could be possibly included in the future version of the MED-GOLD service at a more mature phase of development.

6.3.1.1 GRIDDED DATASETS

In this section we'll report an analysis on the main bioclimatic indicators and two different compound indexes adopted in the MED-GOLD Wine service as described in the two main observational datasets reported in the MED-GOLD Dashboard [RD.4]: ERA5, that with the new released back extension, ERA5-BE, can cover the period 1951-present, and PTHRES, the high resolution observational dataset over Portugal that covers the period 1951-2015 (see [RD.1] and references therein).

In particular, we'll focus on the representation of the main climatological features, i.e. climatological average and interannual standard deviation (STD) over different past periods (1951-1980 vs 1981-2010) to highlight the already ongoing observed changes over the area of interest for wine service (Iberian Peninsula and more specifically the Douro region). The shift of STD can provide some insight about the observed changes in the interannual variability for the indicators of interest of the MED-GOLD Wine service. A stronger interannual variability could imply significant changes in climate features from year to year. Moreover, the STD can provide a measure of the statistical robustness of the observed changes: if the absolute values of the changes exceed the STD, the changes observed can be considered statistically significant.

The relevance of the MED-GOLD Wine service bioclimatic indicators and compound risk indexes has been already highlighted and discussed in [RD.1,RD.2,RD.3,RD.4] and references therein.

This analysis will allow us to better highlight the already ongoing changes of the main bioclimatic features that can heavily impact the wine sector, especially for the key region of the MED-GOLD Wine service: the Douro Valley in the Northern part of Portugal and will provide some additional information to what was reported in the MED-GOLD Dashboard.

Let us also remark that the climatological averages 1981-2010 of the main bioclimatic indicators from the gridded datasets above mentioned over the Douro Valley and the Iberian Peninsula at large can be also obtained directly from the MED-GOLD Dashboard.

The analysis of the main climatological features of two different datasets could also highlight the effects of the spatial resolution (ERA5 around 30km, while PTHRES is at 1km).

6.3.1.1.1 GST

In Fig.6-1a we report the climatological average for the reference period 1981-2010 for the Growing Season average Temperature (GST) from ERA5 reanalysis system.

The black box corresponds to an area that includes the Douro Valley. The climatological average, as expected, reflects the orography of the area with lower temperatures in the northern part of the peninsula and in the northern side of Pyrenees. The highest values can be found over Andalusia (and generally in the southern regions) and in the southern side of Pyrenees. In Fig.6-1b the difference between the reference period 1981-2010 against the 1951-1980 as described in the ERA5-BE system, is shown. As widely expected, the figure exhibits a strong shift towards higher values (up to 2 °C in the Central Eastern part of the area). The observed mean change seems to be statistically significant as the absolute value generally exceeds the STD value over the reference period 1981-2010 (Fig.6-1c). For the reference period, the GST in the western part of the Peninsula was characterised by weaker interannual variability (i.e. negative values in Fig. 6-1d).

Figure 6-1 Main features of GST from ERA5 over the Iberian Peninsula. a) GST averaged over the reference period 1981-2010. b) Changes in GST averaged over the reference period 1981-2010 with respect to previous period 1951-1980. c) Interannual STD of GST over the reference period 1981-2010. d) Changes in STD for GST over reference period 1981-2010 with respect to previous period 1951-1980.

Moving to the main area of interest for the MED-GOLD wine service, Fig.6-2 and Fig.6-3 show the same information but zoomed over the Douro region (enclosed in the black box in fig.6.1a) from ERA5 (and ERA5-BE for the period 1951-80) and PTHRES as well. In Fig 6-2 it is also reported, as a reference, the Douro river and the main administrative borders of the Douro region up to the Porto city close to the seaside. The main physical characteristics of the Douro region, along with its relevance for the wine sector, have been widely described in [RD.5].

The Figs 6-2.a) and Figs 6-2.c) show the climatological averages over the reference period 1981-2010 in ERA5 and PTHRES, respectively, that exhibit a general good agreement, with lower values in the northern part of the region and higher values in the southern side and the lowlands close to the sea. However, the PTHRES shows some relevant high-resolution details that allow us to identify the course of the river where the GST are in general higher than the corresponding values for the surrounding hills. Let us remind that the area is characterised by such a complex orography with very steep slopes that the mean temperatures downscaled to the high resolution of PTHRES (around 1 km) seems to better resemble.

On the other hand, the right column of Fig. 6-2 b-d), that reports the mean differences between the GST averaged over the reference period 1981-2010 against 1951-1980, exhibits some discrepancies, even if in the presence of a general warming. In fact, while in ERA5 (and ERA5-BE for the period 1951-1980) there

are no relative maxima along the Douro river, in PTHRES there is a limited area with an enhanced warming in the eastern part of the region, close to the Spanish borders. This implies a different representation of the air temperature, at least from April to October, for the decades 50s-70s in the two datasets.

Figure 6-2 Main features of GST over the Douro region from different gridded data. a) GST averaged over the reference period 1981-2010 from ERA5 (see Fig.6-1a). b) Changes in GST averaged over the reference period 1981-2010 with respect to previous period 1951-1980 from ERA5 (see Fig.6-1b). c) GST averaged over the reference period 1981-2010 from PTHRES. d) Changes in GST averaged over the reference period 1981-2010 with respect to previous period 1951-1980 from PTHRES.

Also, in terms of STD, that could be considered as a measure of the interannual variability of the GST, the two datasets exhibit quite different features (see Fig. 6-3). Regarding the reference period 1981-2010 in ERA5, the STD of GST is almost constant along the Douro river, with some lower values in correspondence of the river mouth, possibly due to the grid points that include a fraction of the sea. As a matter of fact, the sea points are generally characterised by lower variability (Fig. 6-3a and Fig.6-1c). On the opposite, PTHRES dataset is characterised by overall stronger GST variability (see Fig. 6-3c) with two relative maxima: one on the river mouth and the other one in the eastern part of the region. The same pattern can be also recognised in PTHRES, looking at the differences in the interannual variability of GST over the two periods (Fig.6-3d), while in ERA5 a suppression of variability can be observed in the south and north of the Douro region in the reference period 1981-2010 with respect to the previous decades (Fig. 6-3b).

Figure 6-3 Main features of GST over the Douro region from different gridded data. a) Interannual STD of GST over the reference period 1981-2010 from ERA5 (see Fig.6-1c). b) Changes in STD for GST over the reference period 1981-2010 with respect to previous period 1951-1980 from ERA5 (see Fig.6-1d). c) Interannual STD of GST over the reference period 1981-2010 from PTHRES. d) Changes in STD for GST over the reference period 1981-2010 with respect to previous period 1951-1980 from PTHRES.

6.3.1.1.2 SPR

The mean Spring (21 Apr-21 Jun) Precipitation (SprR) over the Iberian Peninsula for the reference period 1981-2010 in ERA5 has been reported in Fig.6-4a. The stronger rainfall is localised over the Pyrenees and over the North Atlantic coasts. With respect to the previous thirty years, slightly stronger precipitation is present in the northern west corner of the peninsula (Fig.6-4b), while in the eastern side a general reduction can be highlighted. However, the absolute values of the observed changes do not exceed the interannual variability of spring rainfall (Fig.6-c) and so they cannot be considered statistically significant. The interannual variability of SprR is stronger than in the present climate with respect to the previous thirty years over the northern part of Portugal, while lower STD values are observed in the eastern part of the peninsula, in the mountain area of the Pyrenees.

Figure 6-4 Main features of SprR from ERA5 over the Iberian Peninsula. a) SprR averaged over the reference period 1981-2010. b) Changes in SprR averaged over the reference period 1981-2010 with respect to the previous period 1951-1980. c) Interannual STD of SprR over the reference period 1981-2010. d) Changes in STD for SprR over the reference period 1981-2010 with respect to the previous period 1951-1980.

More in detail, in the ERA5 system over the Douro region, we can observe stronger spring precipitation in the western area, closer to the sea, and less precipitation in the Eastern part of the region, close to the Spanish border (Fig.6-5a). This west-east gradient is also present in PTHRES which exhibits quite similar patterns (Fig.6-5c). However, the observed climatological changes look quite different: while in ERA5 (ERA5-BE) no relevant changes occur between the two periods (Fig.6-5b), in PTHRES the southern part of the Douro region experiences a not negligible reduction of precipitation (Fig.6-5d).

Figure 6-5 Main features of SprR over the Douro region from different gridded data. a) SprR averaged over the reference period 1981-2010 from ERA5 (see Fig.6-1a). b) Changes in SprR averaged over the reference period 1981-2010 with respect to previous period 1951-1980 from ERA5 (see Fig.6-1b). c) SprR averaged over the reference period 1981-2010 from PTHRES. d) Changes in SprR averaged over the reference period 1981-2010 with respect to the previous period 1951-1980 from PTHRES.

In terms of representation of the interannual variability of SprR, the two datasets are in close agreement (Fig.6-6): the higher values of STD occur in the northern easter part of the region, in correspondence to the local maximum of precipitation (Fig.6-5). With respect to the past, the interannual variability of the spring precipitation in the present climate is generally higher (Fig.6-6 b,d)

Figure 6-6 Main features of SprR over the Douro region from different gridded data. a) Interannual STD of SprR over the reference period 1981-2010 from ERA5 (see Fig.6-1c). b) Changes in STD for SprR over the reference period 1981-2010 with respect to previous period 1951-1980 from ERA5 (see Fig.6-1d). c) Interannual STD of SprR over the reference period 1981-2010 from PTHRES. d) Changes in STD for SprR over the reference period 1981-2010 with respect to previous period 1951-1980 from PTHRES.

6.3.1.1.3 HARVESTR

The 1981-2010 mean Precipitation during the Harvest period (21 Aug -21 Oct) (HarvestR), as described in ERA5, is reported in Fig. 6-7. The main features of this precipitation indicator (Fig.6-7a) are quite similar to those reported in Fig.6-4a for SprR with higher rainfall amount over Pyrenees and North-western Atlantic coasts where the highest interannual variability is also localised (Fig.6-7c). Over the same region, the period 1981-2010 is characterised by higher rainfall (Fig. 6-7b) with respect to the previous thirty years (even if the changes, not exceeding the mean STD, are weakly statistically significant) and by higher interannual variability, while in the rest of the peninsula the interannual variability tends to be reduced with respect to the period 1951-1980 (ERA5-BE).

Figure 6-7 Main features of HarvestR from ERA5 over the Iberian Peninsula. a) HarvestR averaged over the reference period 1981-2010. b) Changes in HarvestR averaged over the reference period 1981-2010 with respect to previous period 1951-1980. c) Interannual STD of HarvestR over the reference period 1981-2010. d) Changes in STD for HarvestR over the reference period 1981-2010 with respect to the previous period 1951-1980.

Figure 6-8 Main features of HarvestR over the Douro region from different gridded data. a) HarvestR averaged over the reference period 1981-2010 from ERA5 (see Fig.6-1a). b) Changes in HarvestR averaged over the reference period 1981-2010 with respect to previous period 1951-1980 from ERA5 (see Fig.6-1b). c) HarvestR averaged over the reference period 1981-2010 from PTHRES. d) Changes in HarvestR averaged over the reference period 1981-2010 with respect to previous period 1951-1980 from PTHRES.

The mean precipitation for the present reference period during the harvest period over the Douro region in ERA5 and PTHRES (Fig.6-8 a,c) exhibits a spatial pattern quite similar to that already reported for the Spring rainfall (Fig.6-5 a,c). However, the precipitation over the 1981-2010 seems to be generally stronger with respect to the previous period 1951-80 in both the datasets, with values generally higher for ERA5 (Fig.6-8 b,d).

Figure 6-9 Main features of HarvestR over the Douro region from different gridded data. a) Interannual STD of HarvestR over the reference period 1981-2010 from ERA5 (see Fig.6-1c). b) Changes in STD for HarvestR over the reference period 1981-2010 with respect to the previous period 1951-1980 from ERA5 (see Fig.6-1d). c) Interannual STD of HarvestR over the reference period 1981-2010 from PTHRES. d) Changes in STD for HarvestR over the reference period 1981-2010 with respect to previous period 1951-1980 from PTHRES.

Also, in terms of the representation of the interannual variability of HarvestR, the two datasets look quite similar (Fig.6-9) for the main spatial pattern (Fig.6-9 a,c) and the changes with respect to the past (Fig.6-9 b,d): the interannual variability of HarvestR in the present climate seems to be higher north of the Douro river and slightly lower on the southern side.

6.3.1.1.4 SU35

The mean number of days from 1st April to 31st October with mean temperatures above 35°C (SU35-AMJJASO) in ERA5 over the whole Iberian Peninsula is reported in Fig.6-10. As expected, the highest values of SU35 (Fig.6-10a) can be found in the south-western inland areas and over Aragon, which are generally characterized by warmer summer temperatures (see also Fig.6-1). Over the sea the indicator

is identically zero. The main changes with respect to the previous reference period 1951-1980 (Fig.6-10b) closely follow the mean spatial patterns and are localised in the correspondence of the mean maxima (i.e. the rich get richer). Also the STD exhibits the same spatial patterns (Fig.6-10c) and experiences the same positive trend (Fig.6-10d).

Figure 6-10 Main features of SU35 from ERA5 over the Iberian Peninsula. a) SU35 averaged over the reference period 1981-2010. b) Changes in SU35 averaged over the reference period 1981-2010 with respect to the previous period 1951-1980. c) Interannual STD of SU35 over the reference period 1981-2010. d) Changes in STD for SU35 over reference period 1981-2010 with respect to previous period 1951-1980.

Fig.6-11, by comparing ERA5 with PTHRES over the Douro region, highlights the critical role played by the spatial resolution of the datasets when indicators with a fixed temperature threshold have been taken into exam. The mean value for SU35 in ERA5 (Fig.6-11a), in fact, shows a limited relative maximum over the Douro region. In PTHRES (Fig.6-11c), characterised by an higher spatial resolution that can take into account the complex orography of the region, the local maximum is definitely more evident and localised along the course of the river. Similar considerations can be deduced looking at the changes with respect to the past climate (Fig.6-11 b,d): the two datasets describe a similar spatial pattern, consistent with a general warming trend more enhanced in PTHRES where also small scale details can be pointed out. The main changes are localised along the river up to the borders with Spain.

Figure 6-11 Main features of SU35 over the Douro region from different gridded data. a) SU35 averaged over the reference period 1981-2010 from ERA5 (see Fig.6-1a). b) Changes in SU35 averaged over the reference period 1981-2010 with respect to the previous period 1951-1980 from ERA5 (see Fig.6-1b). c) SU35 averaged over the reference period 1981-2010 from PTHRES. d) Changes in SU35 averaged over the reference period 1981-2010 with respect to the previous period 1951-1980 from PTHRES.

The analysis of the interannual variability of SU35 over the Douro region (Fig.6-12) confirms what was already remarked in Fig.6-11 with higher values of STD of SU35 in the eastern part of the region (Fig.6-12 a,c), mostly along the course of the Douro river, where higher values can also be detected in the present climate with respect to the past (Fig. 6-12 b,d).

Figure 6-12 Main features of SU35 over the Douro region from different gridded data. a) Interannual STD of SU35 over the reference period 1981-2010 from ERA5. b) Changes in STD for SU35 over the reference period 1981-2010 with respect to the previous period 1951-1980 from ERA5. c) Interannual STD of SU35 over the reference period 1981-2010 from PTHRES. d) Changes in STD for SU35 over the reference period 1981-2010 with respect to the previous period 1951-1980 from PTHRES.

6.3.1.1.5 WSDI

The spatial distribution for Iberian Peninsula of the mean numbers of days with at least 6 consecutive days when the daily maximum temperature exceeds its 90th percentile (Warm Spell Duration Index- WSDI) during the growing season from 1st April to 31st October (Fig. 6-13) shows relative maxima over Aragon and in the southern side of Pyrennes. The present climate exhibits a clear positive trend with respect to the past period of reference 1951-1980.

Figure 6-13 Main features of WSDI from ERA5 over the Iberian Peninsula. a) WSDI averaged over the reference period 1981-2010. b) Changes in WSDI averaged over the reference period 1981-2010 with respect to previous period 1951-1980. c) Interannual STD of WSDI over the reference period 1981-2010. d) Changes in STD for WSDI over the reference period 1981-2010 with respect to the previous period 1951-1980.

The fine scale details over the Douro region (Fig.6-14) suggest something similar to what already pointed out for SU35 at least for the higher resolution dataset PTHRES. While in ERA5 (Fig.6-14 a,b) the spatial patterns of WSDI are quite homogeneous (Fig.6-14a), PTHRES generally shows values quite higher, suggesting tails of the distribution of the maximum temperature more populated (at least for 6 consecutive days with maximum temperature above the 90th percentile) (Fig.6-14c). Two maxima can be detected in the correspondence of the maxima of the mean temperature already reported in Fig.6-3c, one located over the Douro river mouth (not present at all in ERA5) and the other in the eastern part of the region (present but weaker in ERA5), near the Spanish border. The changes in WSDI for the reference period 1981-2010 with respect to 1951-80 follow the same spatial distribution of the mean values of the present climate (Fig.6-14d) with values, however, higher than the changes described in ERA5 (Fig.6-14b).

Figure 6-14 Main features of WSDI over the Douro region from different gridded data. a) WSDI averaged over the reference period 1981-2010 from ERA5. b) Changes in WSDI averaged over the reference period 1981-2010 with respect to the previous period 1951-1980 from ERA5. c) WSDI averaged over the reference period 1981-2010 from PTHRES. d) Changes in WSDI averaged over the reference period 1981-2010 with respect to the previous period 1951-1980 from PTHRES

The analysis of the interannual STD of WSDI over the Douro region (Fig.6-15) confirms what was already remarked for Fig.6-14: the STD spatial patterns closely follow the distribution of the mean values for each dataset, confirming the discrepancies already highlighted with two relative maxima for PTHRES along the coast and in the eastern part of the region not present at all in ERA5.

Figure 6-15 Main features of WSDI over the Douro region from different gridded data. a) Interannual STD of WSDI over the reference period 1981-2010 from ERA5. b) Changes in STD for WSDI over the reference period 1981-2010 with respect to the previous period 1951-1980 from ERA5. c) Interannual STD of WSDI over the reference period 1981-2010 from PTHRES. d) Changes in STD for WSDI over the reference period 1981-2010 with respect to the previous period 1951-1980 from PTHRES.

6.3.1.1.6 COMPOUND SANITARY RISK INDEX

The Compound Sanitary Risk Index has been specifically developed in the framework of the MED-GOLD Wine service to measure the climate related risk of having relevant disease outbreaks during the growing season. It is computed starting from the statistical distribution in terms of percentiles of three bioclimatic indicators: GST, SprR and HarvestR. The main sources of disease risk have been identified in: High/Low SprR (with very high SprR, the overall sanitary risk is even higher; with high GST, the risk related to SprR is increased); High HarvestR (especially in case of low GST); Low GST.

To be consistent with what is reported in [RD.1] and in the following sections on seasonal forecast outcomes, the percentile of the bioclimatic indicators has been computed using as a reference the hindcast period 1993-2016 (in case of PTHRES the final year is 2015, we have also re-computed the distribution of

ERA5 dropping out 2016 obtaining quite similar results, here showed). The Normalisation has been computed over the whole period. Major details and explanation can be found in [RD.1].

As the index has been co-designed with SOGRAPE starting from the specific conditions of the Douro region, we report here only the results over this area.

Not surprisingly for a normalised index based on the statistical distribution of the bioclimatic indicators, the mean values over the reference period 1981-2010 (Fig.6-16 a,c) do not show local maxima and are quite close to medium risk (i.e. 50 risk units). However, the warming trend observed for GST (Fig.6-2 b,d) implies an overall reduction of pest infestation (Fig. 6-16 b,d). Moreover, in PTHRES (Fig. 6-16d), the reduction of sanitary risk south of the Douro river in the reference period with respect to the past is likely linked to the lower spring rainfall (see Fig. 6-5d) that occurred in the reference period 1981-2010 against the previous thirty years 1951-80.

Figure 6-16 Main features of Compound Sanitary Risk Index over the Douro region from different gridded data. a) Compound Sanitary Risk Index averaged over the reference period 1981-2010 from ERA5. b) Changes in Compound Sanitary Risk Index averaged over the reference period 1981-2010 with respect to previous period 1951-1980 from ERA5. c) Compound Sanitary Risk Index averaged over the reference period 1981-2010 from PTHRES. d) Changes in Compound Sanitary Risk Index averaged over the reference period 1981-2010 with respect to previous period 1951-1980 from PTHRES

The mean representation of the interannual variability of the Sanitary Risk Index over the reference period exhibits different features in the two datasets in exam (Fig. 6-17 b-d). This can be mostly due to different patterns reported for instance in Fig.6-3 a,c. In ERA5 high variability can be found in the north-eastern part of the region, while in PTHRES high values can be found also in south-western corner. However, both datasets report an overall higher variability in the present climate with respect to the past (Fig.6-17 b,d), with a partial exception in ERA5 for the northern bank of the Douro river

Figure 6-17 Main features of Compound Sanitary Risk Index over the Douro region from different gridded data. a) Interannual STD of Compound Sanitary Risk Index over the reference period 1981-2010 from ERA5. b) Changes in STD for Compound Sanitary Risk Index over the reference period 1981-2010 with respect to the previous period 1951-1980 from ERA5. c) Interannual STD of Compound Sanitary Risk Index over the reference period 1981-2010 from PTHRES. d) Changes in STD for Compound Sanitary Risk Index over the reference period 1981-2010 with respect to the previous period 1951-1980 from PTHRES.

6.3.1.1.7 COMPOUND HEAT RISK INDEX

The Compound Heat Risk Index has been specifically developed in the framework of the MED-GOLD Wine service to measure the climate related risk of heat damage for the grapes during the growing season. It is computed starting from the statistical distribution in terms of percentiles of three bioclimatic indicators: GST, SU35 and WSDI.

Analogously to the Sanitary Risk index, to be consistent with what is reported in [RD.1] and in the following sections on seasonal forecast outcomes, the percentile of the bioclimatic indicators has been computed using as a reference the hindcast period 1993-2016. Additional details and explanations can be found in [RD.1].

As expected, considering the quite different mean features reported in the previous sections for the climatological averages of SU35 and WSDI in ERA5 and PTHRES (Figs. 6-11; 6-14), the mean spatial patterns of the Heat Risk Index in the two datasets exhibit some differences (Fig.6-18). In particular PTHRES is characterised by higher values, especially along the course of the river (Fig.6-18c).

The consolidated warming trend in the last decades, well reported in the previous subsections, clearly leads to higher values of Heat Risk index with respect to the period 1951-80 (Fig.6-18 b,d).

Figure 6-18 Main features of Compound Heat Risk Index over the Douro region from different gridded data. a) Compound Heat Risk Index averaged over the reference period 1981-2010 from ERA5. b) Changes in Compound Heat Risk Index averaged over the reference period 1981-2010 with respect to the previous period 1951-1980 from ERA5. c) Compound Heat Risk Index averaged over the reference period 1981-2010 from PTHRES. d) Changes in Compound Heat Risk Index averaged over the reference period 1981-2010 with respect to previous period 1951-1980 from PTHRES

While the mean STD for 1981-2010 exhibits similar patterns for the two datasets (Fig.6-19a-c), with higher values can be found mainly south of the Douro river and in Vila Real district north of the river.

However, the interannual variability of Heat Risk is generally higher in the present climate with respect to the past decades ((Fig.6-19 b,d).

Figure 6-19 Main features of Compound Heat Risk Index over the Douro region from different gridded data. a) Interannual STD of Compound Heat Risk Index over the reference period 1981-2010 from ERA5. b) Changes in STD for Compound Heat Risk Index over the reference period 1981-2010 with respect to the previous period 1951-1980 from ERA5. c) Interannual STD of Compound Heat Risk Index over the reference period 1981-2010 from PTHRES. d) Changes in STD for Compound Heat Risk Index over the reference period 1981-2010 with respect to the previous period 1951-1980 from PTHRES

6.3.1.1.8 RECONSTRUCTING THE MAIN INDICATORS OF THE MED-GOLD WINE SERVICE FOR THE PAST CLIMATE IN GRIDDED DATASETS: A BRIEF SUMMARY

The climate for the reference period 1981-2010 with respect to 1951-1980 over the region of interest for the MED-GOLD wine service is generally warmer, and characterised by slightly more intense spring precipitation. This leads to a general reduction of the risk of the need of additional sanitary treatments and an increase of possible heat stress for the grapes.

Looking at the two main gridded datasets present in the dashboard some main results can be summarised:

- Close agreement in the main representation of precipitation, with some discrepancies raised for past climate, especially south of the Douro river;
- Mean temperature discrepancies can be pointed out in the representation of 1951-1980;
- In PTHRES it's visible a relative maximum of temperature close to the mouth of the Douro river not present in ERA5, in general small scale details linked to a more detailed representation of the complex orography of the area;
- The critical role is played by the spatial resolution of the datasets when extreme indicators with a fixed temperature threshold have been taken into exam (SU35)
- In PTHRES more populated tails of the maximum temperature distribution (at least 6 consecutive days above 90th percentile);
- The above results lead to some consequent discrepancies in the representation of the MED-GOLD compound risk indexes (e.g higher mean risk of heat stress in PTHRES, different spatial distribution of STDin the Sanitary risk index).

6.3.1.2 EXAMPLE OF BIOCLIMATIC INDICATORS OBTAINED BY SATELLITE

The exploitation of the open Copernicus program as well as the Landsat program provide valuable information to monitor the evolution, development and almost real time status of plants considering the relation between the biological activity of the plants and the spectral responses detected by the Earth Observation sensors. In the frame of the MED-GOLD project, different indexes were calculated to be used as ancillary information, which add value to the Climate data provided through the different MED-GOLD services such as the dashboard. For the grape/wine sector, five indices have been calculated based on different available satellite imagery in three spatial resolutions which allow exploration in different detail levels. The table 6-1 summarizes the indices calculated by sensor and time.

Table 6-1 Indices based on remote sensing for wine sector

satellite	index	spatial resolution (meters)	time interval	cover area	files
S2	NDVI	20	2017 to 2020	Douro Region	55
S2	NDWI	20	2018 to 2020	Douro Region	55
L8	NDVI	30	2019 to 2020	Douro Region	54
L8	NDWI	30	2013 to 2020	Douro Region	54
L8	LST	30	2014 to 2020	Douro Region	54
L8	TVX	30	2015 to 2020	Douro Region	54

MODIS	NDVI	450	2000 to 2020	North Iberian Peninsula	937
MODIS	NDWI	450	2010 to 2020	North Iberian Peninsula	937
MODIS	NMDI	450	2002 to 2020	North Iberian Peninsula	938

Although the different satellites used cover different areas along Northern Portugal, is relevant to highlight the added value that provides the scale which the user can perform analysis to decision making. The Figure 6-20 shows an analysis on a particular vineyard using indices based on MODIS for the year .

Figure 6-20: Indices based on MODIS available to the wine sector.

Flexibility allows to extract information for a particular parcel in a particular period of time. The Figure 6-21 shows the NDVI comparison between two parcels (provided by the partner SOGRAPE) between 2000 and 2020. This kind of results allows monitoring the vineyards and then to compare the results with climate historical data.

Figure 6-21: NDVI time series (2000-2020) in two parcels (“parcel 25” and “parcel4”) located in the Douro Region

In general periodic time series, in this case, NDVI applied to crops, allows to see indirectly variations related to phenology, crops health, etc.

According to the needs exposed by the wine sector in the framework of the MED-GOLD project, some bioclimatic indices are available on the ICT platform which are of importance for this sector. An analysis

between indices based on remote sensing as well as some of these bioclimatic indices can help to decide more clearly which actions to take in the future.

The Figure 6-22 shows the NMDI, NDWI and NDVI on a test parcel during the period from April to October 2019 (GST and HarvestR are calculated in this period)

Figure 6-22: indices based on remote sensing during April to October 2019

The GST for the area that contains the testing parcel had a value of 21.2°C in 2015 (Figure 6-23). These results combined with indices based on satellites time series provide extra information for users.

Figure 6-23: GST during 2015 and general visualization of the vineyard (“Parcel 4”)

As mentioned before, the indexes have been calculated based on three available sensors, this allows, considering the spatial resolution, to observe in detail the status of the crops.

In the framework of the wine sector, additional to MODIS imagery, high resolution indices were calculated using Landsat8 and Sentinel 2. In the case of LST and TVX, only Landsat8 provides the thermal bands for calculations. NDVI and NDWI were calculated using both sources. Observations on the parcel can combine both results (L8 and S2) to mitigate the gaps due to differences in the revisit period. The Figure 6-24 shows an example of the behaviour of the test parcel during the first semester of 2020 using Landst8 for calculations. The inconvenience of the revisit period (time elapsed between observations of the same point on Earth by a satellite) as well as cloud cover can be observed in the Figure 6-25 where the variations are not smooth. This inconvenient also can be observed in Sentinel 2 derived products (Figure 6-26)

Figure 6-24: Indices based on Landsat 8 in “Parcel 22” during the first semester of 2020

Figure 6-25: LST and NDVI variations from 2013 to 2020 in “parcel 22”

.Figure 6-26: NDWI based on Sentinel 2 comparison from 2017 to 2020 on “parcel 22”

The analysis of the indices calculated for the wine sector must be done at scales at which the Earth observation data have added value. Although the spatial resolution at which the climate and bioclimatic indicators are calculated corresponds to large scales (2.5km or more), the indices based on remote sensing demonstrate the periodicity that corresponds to variations in phenology (NDVI) and climate (NDWI, LST, NMDI). These assumptions are clearly manifested by observing season to season trends or the differences between parcels located close to Douro river and parcels located in other areas. Unfortunately, products based on EO depend on ideal conditions like low cloud cover, revisit periods, no errors in bands, etc. and this supposes the combination with other ancillary data.

It's relevant to remark that the role of data calculated from high resolution imagery is to provide information near to real-time which, compared with climate and bioclimatic data, can indicate how could be the behaviour of a crop under a hypothetical future climate condition.

6.3.2 SEASONAL FORECAST OVER THE AREAS OF INTEREST FOR THE MED-GOLD WINE SERVICE

This section summarises the performance of seasonal predictions of Essential Climate Variables (ECVs), bioclimatic indicators (GST, GDD, WSDI, SprR, HaverstR and SU35) and risk indices (Compound Heat Risk and Compound Sanitary risk index) over the Douro valley (Portugal) and the Iberian Peninsula. The analysis of these three information layers gives a complete picture of the quality of the seasonal prediction information the project is providing to the wine users.

The assessment of the quality (skill) of seasonal predictions is achieved by systematically comparing predictions of the past with an observational reference dataset (i.e. what actually happened) and deriving statistical measures from this comparison. This process is also known as 'verification analysis'. When such measures are skill scores it means they assess the performance of a climate prediction in relation to a standard (i.e. the alternative to using the prediction) such as the historical average (climatology). In general, we say a prediction has skill (skill scores greater than zero) when the number of times the prediction matches the observation is higher than the number of times the historical average matches the same observation. In these cases, using the climate prediction for making decisions is better than using the historical average. Conversely, when skill scores are less than zero, the prediction does not have skill, which means that it is better not to use it for decision-making.

The verification has been performed by assessing the bias, the Fair Ranked Probability Skill Score (FRPSS) and the ensemble mean correlation between the ECMWF System 5 (SEAS5) and the ERA5 reference dataset. In order to avoid the smoothing of extremes, the seasonal predictions have been interpolated to the ERA5 grid with a bicubic algorithm. On the other hand, the biases have been corrected with a simple bias correction method. These approaches have been detailed in [RD.1]. Regarding this verification, although it has been completed for all the months and lead-times, in this deliverable only the results of the verification for the April start date are shown because of its relevance for the wine sector (it is at the beginning of the vine growing season, April-to-October, the most interesting from the wine sector perspective). Finally, since the performance of some of the indicators might be somewhat limited, we put forward a promising strategy to improve the skill of the predictions while maintaining an effective level of usability for the user. This approach consists in blending observations and forecasts as the growing season progresses. We have evaluated the impact of this possibility, with the GST indicator.

6.3.2.1. ESSENTIAL CLIMATE VARIABLES

This subsection reports the results from the assessment of the MED-GOLD so-called Essential Climate Variables (ECVs): mean temperature, maximum temperature, minimum temperature and precipitation (at monthly frequency). In each case the prediction performance (SEAS5) compared to the reference dataset (ERA5) is presented through four figures: the climatology from the reference ERA5, the SEAS5 remaining bias after being bias-adjusted (to be able to infer how close is the climatology from bias-adjusted SEAS5 to the ERA5 one), and two skill metrics, ensemble mean correlation and FRPSS. These metrics have been obtained over the period 1993-2016, for which the predictions of the past (also known as hindcasts) are available. In this case, only the verification for May (lead 1, April start Month) is presented. It is also important to note that a wider picture of ECVs verification for Europe was already provided in [RD.6] for different forecast systems.

6.3.2.1.1 PRECIPITATION

May precipitation (figure figure 6-27 a) is higher along the northern and northwestern shores of the Iberian Peninsula, as well as over the main mountain ranges (i.e. the Pyrenees). Bias-adjusted SEAS5 prediction for May (April start month) shows biases lying in the -1 to 3mm (per month) range (figure 6-27 b). The skill is scattered around different areas of the Iberian Peninsula, but without following any clear spatial pattern (see 6-27 c and d). The Douro Valley does not show any positive skill for this particular start month and time horizon.

Figure 6-27. Statistics for May precipitation over the Iberian Peninsula and the Douro Valley (black contour) considering the period 1993-2016. The seasonal prediction system is ECMWF System 5 (SEAS5) with predictions issued in April for forecasting May. The forecast has been bias corrected with a simple bias correction algorithm. The reference dataset is ERA5. The statistics are: (a) ERA5 climatology (b) Remaining monthly precipitation Bias after the application of the bias-adjustment method to the SEAS5 (c) Pearson Ensemble mean Correlation between SEAS5 and ERA5 and (d) Fair Ranked Probability Skill Score (FRPSS).

6.3.2.1.2 MEAN, MAXIMUM AND MINIMUM TEMPERATURES

May mean temperature (figure 6-28 a) has its highest values in the southwestern Iberian Peninsula, the Mediterranean coast and the Ebro Valley. The monthly bias, after SEAS5 correction, is contained between -1°C and 1°C (figure 6-28 b). The ensemble correlation and FRPSS (figure 6-28 c and d) show positive values in most of the inner Iberian Peninsula (except in the north and northeast). Regarding the Douro Valley, it displays FRPSS values up to 0.1. This behaviour is similarly reproduced both for the maximum (figure figure 6-29) and minimum temperatures (figure 6-30).

Figure 6-28. Statistics for May mean temperature over the Iberian Peninsula and the Douro Valley (black contour) considering the period 1993-2016. The seasonal prediction system is ECMWF System 5 (SEAS5) with predictions issued in April for forecasting May. The forecast has been bias corrected with a simple bias correction algorithm. The reference dataset is ERA5. The statistics are: (a) ERA5 climatology (b) Remaining Bias after the application of the bias-adjustment method to the SEAS5 (c) Pearson Ensemble mean Correlation between SEAS5 and ERA5 and (d) Fair Ranked Probability Skill Score (FRPSS).

Figure 6-29. Statistics for May mean maximum temperature over the Iberian Peninsula and the Douro Valley (black contour) considering the period 1993-2016. The seasonal prediction system is ECMWF System 5 (SEAS5) with predictions issued in April for forecasting May. The forecast has been bias corrected with a simple bias correction algorithm. The reference dataset is ERA5. The statistics are: (a) ERA5 climatology (b) Remaining Bias after the application of the bias-adjustment method to the SEAS5 (c) Pearson Ensemble mean Correlation between SEAS5 and ERA5 and (d) Fair Ranked Probability Skill Score (FRPSS).

Figure 6-30. Statistics for May mean minimum temperature over the Iberian Peninsula and the Douro Valley (black contour) considering the period 1993-2016. The seasonal prediction system is ECMWF System 5 (SEAS5) with predictions issued in April for forecasting May. The forecast has been bias corrected with a simple bias correction algorithm. The reference dataset is ERA5. The statistics are: (a) ERA5 climatology (b) Remaining Bias after the application of the bias-adjustment method to the SEAS5 (c) Pearson Ensemble mean Correlation between SEAS5 and ERA5 and (d) Fair Ranked Probability Skill Score (FRPSS).

6.3.2.2. INDICATORS

The indicators assessed in this section are the ones chosen by the wine sector end-users in the co-production process, corresponding to those indices more useful from a wine-producer perspective: Growing Season Temperature (GST, mean temperature from the 1st of April to 31st of October), Spring Rain (SprR, accumulated precipitation from 21st April to 21st June), Harvest Rain (HarvestR, accumulated precipitation from 21st August to 21st October), Growing Degree Days (GDD, sum of the differences between daily mean temperatures and 10°C, from the 1st of April to 31st of October. However, this indicator is redundant with respect to GST and it's not reported in the MED-GOLD Dashboard), Heat Stress Days (SU35, number of days from the 1st April to 31st October with maximum temperatures above 35°C) and Warm Spell Duration Index (WSDI, number of days counted when 6 consecutive days have mean temperatures above 90th percentile from 1st of April to 31st October). The methods to obtain and compute these indicators have been reported in [RD.1]. Regarding the verification performed, it is analogous to the one described in subsection 6.3.2.1.

6.3.2.2.1 GST

The GST highest values are in the southwestern part of the Iberian Peninsula (with a maximum in the Guadalquivir Valley), the Ebro Valley and the Mediterranean coasts. The lowest values, on the other hand, lie in the north (see also Fig. 6-1). The Douro Valley has a west-east gradient, with higher values in the eastern inner Douro. Regarding the bias, the deviation of the bias-corrected modelled climatology is constrained between 1°C and -1°C (Fig. 6-31). In general, this indicator has positive skill, both for the ensemble correlation and the FRPSS. In this case, although there is no clear geographical pattern, the greatest values tend to be in the north and southeastern of the Iberian Peninsula. As for the Douro Valley, the larger positive values can be seen in the eastern region (up to 0.2).

Figure 6-31. Statistics for the GST index (mean season temperature from April to October) over the Iberian Peninsula and the Douro Valley (black contour) considering the period 1993-2016. The seasonal prediction system is ECMWF System 5 (SEAS5) and the verified start month, April. The forecast has been bias corrected with a simple bias correction algorithm. The reference dataset is ERA5. The statistics are: (a) ERA5 climatology (b) Remaining Bias after the application of the bias-adjustment method to the SEAS5 (c) Pearson Ensemble mean Correlation between SEAS5 and ERA5 and (d) Fair Ranked Probability Skill Score (FRPSS).

6.3.2.2.2 SprR

Figure 6-32 a) shows the SprR has its maximum values also in the north and northwest of the Iberian Peninsula (especially in northern Portugal, Galicia, the Cantabric shores and the Pyrenees) (see also Fig.6-4). In these areas it ranges from 300mm to 500mm, being lower in the rest. Douro Valley exhibits a west-east gradient, decreasing to the east, with quantities ranging from 100mm to 300mm. The verification of the bias corrected SEAS5 shows it differs from this climatology in the range between -30mm to 30mm. In this case the skill is limited to the tercile approach. The ensemble correlation is almost null in all the Iberian Peninsula, as it can be seen in 6-32 c). The FRPSS, on the contrary, shows positive values everywhere except in the north and northwest, where they are scarce or zero (see 6-32 d). In the Douro Valley these skill metrics are null, which means that for April start month and this indicator it is better to use climatology instead of the predictions.

Figure 6-32. Statistics for the SprR index (accumulated precipitation from 21st April to 21st June) over the Iberian Peninsula and the Douro Valley (black contour) considering the period 1993-2016. The seasonal prediction system is ECMWF System 5 (SEAS5) and the verified start month, April. The forecast has been bias corrected with a simple bias correction algorithm. The reference dataset is ERA5. The statistics are: (a) ERA5 climatology (b) Remaining Bias after the application of the bias-adjustment method to the SEAS5 (c) Pearson Ensemble mean Correlation between SEAS5 and ERA5 and (d) Fair Ranked Probability Skill Score (FRPSS).

6.3.2.2.3 HARVESTR

As also reported in Fig.6-7, HarvestR climatology (1993-2016) maximum values lie in the north and northwest of the Iberian Peninsula, (fig 6-33 a) . In these areas it ranges from a minimum of 300mm to more than 500mm (in the western Pyrennees and northern coast of Portugal). In the rest, the amounts are below this threshold. Douro Valley displays quantities ranging from 100mm to 300mm, with lower values in the eastern Douro. The bias corrected SEAS5 is in agreement with this distribution with bias values contained within the -30mm to 30mm range (mainly positive). HarvestR shows the greater skill in the western part of the Iberian Peninsula, the one with the higher Atlantic influence. This is true looking both at the correlation and the FRPSS, fig 6-33 c) and d). The Douro Valley is within this area and, thus, displays an analogous behaviour.

Figure 6-33. Statistics for the HaverstR (accumulated precipitation from 21st August to 21st October) over the Iberian Peninsula and the Douro Valley (black contour) considering the period 1993-2016. The seasonal prediction system is ECMWF System 5 (SEAS5) and the verified start month, April. The forecast has been bias corrected with a simple bias correction algorithm. The reference dataset is ERA5. The statistics are: (a) ERA5 climatology (b) Remaining Bias after the application of the bias-adjustment method to the SEAS5 (c) Pearson Ensemble mean Correlation between SEAS5 and ERA5 and (d) Fair Ranked Probability Skill Score (FRPSS).

6.3.2.2.4 GDD

The GDD also displays the highest values in the southwestern part of the Iberian Peninsula, the Ebro Valley and the Mediterranean coasts (normally, the warmest climate regions in this period). In these areas, the GDD ranges from 500 to more than 1000 degrees (see 6-34 a). The Douro Valley, on the other hand, has GDD between 250 to 500 degrees. The bias, after correction, is almost non-existent with values between 1 and -1 degrees. Regarding the skill metrics, correlation and FRPSS, their spatial distribution does not show a distinct geographical pattern, but in the Douro Valley we can find positive FRPSS values from 0.05 to 0.2. This index is closely linked to the GST and, hence, the construction of the compound risk indices considered only one of them (GST). Hence, it's not reported in the MED-GOLD Dashboard.

Figure 6-34. Statistics for the GDD index (growing degree days accumulated from April to October) over the Iberian Peninsula and the Douro Valley (black contour) considering the period 1993-2016. The seasonal prediction system is ECMWF System 5 (SEAS5) and the verified start month, April. The forecast has been bias corrected with a simple bias correction algorithm. The reference dataset is ERA5. The statistics are: (a) ERA5 climatology (b) Remaining Bias after the application of the bias-adjustment method to the SEAS5 (c) Pearson Ensemble mean Correlation between SEAS5 and ERA5 and (d) Fair Ranked Probability Skill Score (FRPSS).

6.3.2.2.5 SU35

In figure 6-35 it can be seen that the warmest areas of the Iberian Peninsula are the ones displaying the highest climatic values (6-35 a), namely the Guadalquivir Valley (more than 30 days/season) and the surrounding regions (from 10 to 30 days/season), with another secondary area in the Ebro Valley (up to 20 days/season) (see also Fig.6-10). The rest, including Douro Valley, show values up to 10 days/season. The bias of the model after bias correction is very low, between 0 and 1 days/season. Finally, regarding the skill, it is focused in the southeastern centre interior of the Iberian Peninsula.

Figure 6-35. Statistics for the SU35 indicator (number of days from April to October with maximum temperatures above 35°C) over the Iberian Peninsula and the Douro Valley (black contour) considering the period 1993-2016. The seasonal prediction system is ECMWF System 5 (SEAS5) and the verified start month, April. The forecast has been bias corrected with a simple bias correction algorithm. The reference dataset is ERA5. The statistics are: (a) ERA5 climatology (b) Remaining Bias after the application of the bias-adjustment method to the SEAS5 (c) Pearson Ensemble mean Correlation between SEAS5 and ERA5 and (d) Fair Ranked Probability Skill Score (FRPSS).

6.3.2.2.6 WSDI

The WSDI in figure 6-36 shows a spatial distribution which is centred in the easter interior of the Iberian Peninsula, with values between 12 and 24 days/season (see also Fig.-6-13). The Douro Valley has a mean accumulation between 8 and 12 days/season. Regarding the bias of the modelled climatology after being bias-corrected, it is reduced to -1 or 1 days/season. In this case, there is no skill either with the ensemble mean correlation or the FRPSS, in any region of the Iberian Peninsula. This means that for WSDI, in most of the places and, also, for the Douro Valley, in April it is better to use the seasonal average than the seasonal prediction.

Figure 6-36. Statistics for WSDI (number of days counted when 6 consecutive days have mean temperatures above 90th percentile from April to October) considering the period 1993-2016. The seasonal prediction system is ECMWF System 5 (SEAS5) and the verified start month, April. The forecast has been bias corrected with a simple bias correction algorithm. The reference dataset is ERA5. The statistics are: (a) ERA5 climatology (b) Remaining Bias after the application of the bias-adjustment method to the SEAS5 (c) Pearson Ensemble mean Correlation between SEAS5 and ERA5 and (d) Fair Ranked Probability Skill Score (FRPSS).

6.3.2.3. RISK INDEXES

AS already described in sec 6.3.1.1.6 and 6.3.1.1.7 (and references therein), the Compound Sanitary and Heat Risk Indexes are a combination of multiple bioclimatic indicators. Since these indicators refer to specific periods of time within the growing season (April to October), they combine seasonal predictions from different variables and lead times. More specifically:

- Sanitary risk: combination of GST (1st April to 31st October), SprR (21st April to 21st June) and HarvestR (21st August to 21st October).
- Heat risk: combination of SU35 (1st April to 31st October), WSDI (April to October) and GST (April to Oct).

6.3.2.3.1 COMPOUND SANITARY RISK INDEX

The sanitary index (figure 6-37) assessment is also reported through the FRPSS for the same start months as for the heat index: March (a), April (b), May (c) and June (d). The higher values are found in April and May start dates and for the northern and eastern. In the remaining areas and start months the skill is mainly negative.

Figure 6-37 Fair Ranked Probability Skill Score (FRPSS) of the sanitary risk index for four starting months (a) March (b) April (c) May and (d) June. Positive (negative) values refer to better (worse) skill than climatology.

6.3.2.3.2 COMPOUND HEAT RISK INDEX

Figure 6-38 depicts the FRPSS for the Compound Heat Risk Index for four start months: March (a), April (b), May (c) and June (d). Douro Valley and nearby areas show predominantly negative FRPSS values, meaning the use of climatology gives better results than the SEAS5 predictions. However, there are still regions where the skill is positive, especially in June start date and for the eastern Douro.

6-38. Fair Ranked Probability Skill Score (FRPSS) of the heat risk index for four starting months (a) March (b) April (c) May and (d) June. Positive (negative) values refer to better (worse) skill than climatology.

6.3.2.4. EFFECT OF BLENDING OBSERVATIONS AND FORECAST DURING THE SEASON

The vine growing season, from April to October, is the most important period for the wine sector. It is when the different phenological stages develop and, hence, it is the time interval where the most important decisions are made (pest control treatments, labour hiring, harvest date start point, etc.). Consequently, it is when the seasonal forecasts could have the greatest impact on user's strategic decisions. However, sometimes the limited skill of some indicators holds back the potential application of these predictions. To overcome this situation this section puts forward the results obtained when trying to increase the skill of the forecasts by merging observations and predictions as the growing season progresses.

6.3.2.4.1 GST

Looking at FRPSS (figure 6-39) it can be seen that there is a progression from values up to 0.2 in April (without no observations) to widespread 0.8 in September (including observations from April to August). The same happens when observing the correlation (figure 6-40), which starts in April with values from 0.1 to 0.5, and reaches values above 0.9 in September. The most important feature that needs to be highlighted, is that this upward trend is seen through all the start months as the season progresses. Actually, this is a very interesting aspect for the user, because he can choose, depending on the decision, the month in which the trade-off between having antecedent and skillful information is best for his interests.

Figure 6-39. FRPSS for the GST (mean season temperature from April to October) over the Iberian Peninsula and the Douro Valley (black contour) considering the period 1993-2016. The seasonal prediction system is ECMWF System 5 (SEAS5) and the verified start month, April. The forecast has been bias corrected with a simple bias correction algorithm. The reference dataset is ERA5. Each map represents a specific combination: (a) only predicted leads (b) April (observed) + May to October (predicted) (c) April to May (observed) + June to October (predicted) (d) April to June (observed) + July to October (predicted) (e) April to July (observed) + August to October (predicted) (f) April to August (observed) + September to October (predicted).

Figure 6-40. Ensemble correlation for the GST (mean season temperature from April to October) over the Iberian Peninsula and the Douro Valley (black contour) considering the period 1993-2016. The seasonal prediction system is ECMWF System 5 (SEAS5) and the verified start month, April. The forecast has been bias corrected with a simple bias correction algorithm. The reference dataset is ERA5. Each map represents a specific combination: (a) only predicted leads (b) April (observed) + May to October (predicted) (c) April to May (observed) + June to October (predicted) (d) April to June (observed) + July to October (predicted) (e) April to July (observed) + August to October (predicted) (f) April to August (observed) + September to October (predicted).

6.3.2.5 SUMMARY OF THE RESULTS

This subsection reports the outcomes of the quality assessment of seasonal predictions for ECVs, bioclimatic indicators and compound risk indexes over the Iberian Peninsula and the Douro valley (Portugal). The results show the bias-adjustment allows a close reproduction of the observed climatology in all the predicted ECVs and bioclimatic indicators. In the case of ECVs, temperature usually gives better skill than precipitation. Regarding the bioclimatic indicators, the skill depends on its nature. In general, the more extreme an indicator, the more difficult to forecast it. Particularly, GST and GDD display the best quality. Considering the GST 'blending experiment', there is an increase in skill as we enter the season and more observations are included in the indicator. This is an interesting feature because it allows the user to optimize the moment to make a decision (the best trade-off between anticipation and expected quality).

Finally, the compound risk indexes show some potential in the Douro region, specially in the inner / northern Douro and some specific start dates (i.e. June for the Heat Index and April and May, for the Sanitary Index).

6.3.3 CLIMATE PROJECTIONS OVER THE AREAS OF INTEREST FOR THE MED-GOLD WINE SERVICE

In this section the changes due to climate change for the relevant bioclimatic indicators are presented using a sub-ensemble of five bias adjusted Regional Climate Models ([RD.3] and [RD.1]) from the EURO-CORDEX modelling experiment. The compound risk indexes have not been computed over the climate projections as in the interaction with users it has been highlighted that there was a limited interest in this kind of risk measurements over the long-term projections (as reported in [RD.2] and [RD.4]). As a matter of fact, the compound risk indexes have been developed measuring the risk starting from the present climate: in this perspective, their main application should be in the reconstruction of past/present climate and in seasonal forecast.

The horizontal resolution of the models is 1km [RD.1] while the simulated data in this study covers three periods: the 1971-2000 which is used as the reference period and the periods 2031-2060 and 2071-2100 under two Representative Concentration Pathways (RCP) scenarios, the RCP4.5 and RCP8.5. For each of the indices, at each grid point over the Douro area, the changes between the future periods and the reference one are considered robust, when the changes in at least three out of five models are found statistically significant and when the change in the same models is of the same sign. The first criterion is examined by using the 95th percentile confidence intervals as derived by bootstrap. If only one of the criteria is met, the change at the specific grid point is not considered significant [RD.7].

6.3.3.1 GST

In Fig.6-41 the changes between the future periods and the reference one for the GST are shown. In general robust increases for the whole area of interest are projected for both the two future periods and under both future scenarios. In particular for the near future period (2031-2060), the average increases are about 1.7°C and 2°C under RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 respectively. Regarding the distant future period (2071-2100), the average increases are about 2.4°C and about 4.3°C under RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 respectively.

Figure 6-41 Mean absolute changes in the growing season temperature (GST) for the five member model sub-ensemble between the near (2031-2060) and the distant future (2071-2100) periods and the reference one (1971-2000) under both RCP scenarios (RCP4.5 and RCP8.5). In each panel M denotes the spatial average change over all the grid points covering the area with the units being the same as in the colorbar. Black dots indicate a robust change at the grid point scale while N denotes the percentage of grid points where robust changes are found

6.3.3.2 SPRR

Regarding SprR, the projected decrease for the two future periods are shown in Fig. 6-42 with respect to the reference period under both RCP scenarios. In particular, for the near future period the average relative decrease ranges from about 15% to 21% per season under RCP4.5 and RCP8.5, respectively. However, the changes are not found robust for all the grid points under RCP4.5, while robust decrease is found for 19% of the grid points under RCP8.5, covering the western, north-eastern, and eastern areas. For the distant future, higher relative decreases in SprR is shown, reaching about 23% and 34% per season under RCP4.5

and RCP8.5, respectively. In addition, the percentage of grid points where these changes are found robust is 65% and 95% for the two scenarios, respectively.

Figure 6-42 Mean relative changes in the spring precipitation (SprR) for the five member model sub-ensemble between the near (2031-2060) and the distant future (2071-2100) periods and the reference one (1971-2000) under both RCP scenarios (RCP4.5 and RCP8.5). In each panel M denotes the spatial average change over all the grid points covering the area with the units being the same as in the colorbar. Black dots indicate a robust change at the grid point scale while N denotes the percentage of grid points where robust changes are found

6.3.3.3 HARVESTR

Lower relative decreases compared to SprR are shown for HarvestR (here reported as HarvR) (Fig. 6-43). For the near future period, the average relative decreases range from about 8% to 15% per season under RCP4.5 and RCP8.5, respectively. Nevertheless, under both scenarios the changes are not found

robust. For the distant future higher relative decreases in HarvestR are shown reaching about 16% and 30% per season under RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 respectively. Nevertheless under RCP4.5 the changes are not found robust for all of the grid points in the area while under RCP8.5 robust decreases are found for the majority of grid points covering the area.

Figure 6-43 Mean relative changes in the precipitation during harvest (HarvR) for the five member model sub-ensemble between the near (2031-2060) and the distant future (2071-2100) periods and the reference one (1971-2000) under both RCP scenarios (RCP4.5 and RCP8.5). In each panel M denotes the spatial average change over all the grid points covering the area with the units being the same as in the colorbar. Black dots indicate a robust change at the grid point scale while N denotes the percentage of grid points where robust changes are found

6.3.3.4 GDD

In Fig. 6-44 the relative changes between the two future periods under both future scenarios and the reference one are shown for GDD. From the figure it is evident that robust relative increases are projected for all periods and scenarios examined. For the near future period the average relative increases projected under RCP4.5 are about 24% whereas under RCP8.5 the increases reach about 28%. Regarding the distant future higher relative increases in GDD are shown reaching about 33% and 60% under RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 respectively.

Figure 6-44 Mean relative changes in the growing degree days (GDD) for the five member model sub-ensemble between the near (2031-2060) and the distant future (2071-2100) periods and the reference one (1971-2000) under both RCP scenarios (RCP4.5 and RCP8.5). In each panel M denotes the spatial average change over all the grid points covering the area with the units being the same as in the colorbar. Black dots indicate a robust change at the grid point scale while N denotes the percentage of grid points where robust changes are found

6.3.3.5 SU35

In figure 6-44 the absolute changes between the reference and the two future periods under both future scenarios are shown for SU35. From the figure it is evident that robust increases are projected for all periods and scenarios examined. For the near future period the average increase projected under RCP4.5 is about 9 extra days/season, whereas under RCP8.5 the increase reaches about 12 extra days/season. Regarding the distant future, higher average increase is shown, reaching about 13 and 36 extra

days/season under RCP4.5 and RCP8.5, respectively. It should be mentioned that under all periods and scenarios the highest increases are shown along the course of the river while lower increases are shown for the surrounding hills.

Figure 6-45 Mean absolute changes in the number of summer heat stress days (SU35) for the five member model sub-ensemble between the near (2031-2060) and the distant future (2071-2100) periods and the reference one (1971-2000) under both RCP scenarios (RCP4.5 and RCP8.5). In each panel M denotes the spatial average change over all the grid points covering the area with the units being the same as in the colorbar. Black dots indicate a robust change at the grid point scale while N denotes the percentage of grid points where robust changes are found

6.3.3.6 WSDI

In figure 6-45 the absolute changes between the reference and the two future periods under both future scenarios are shown for WSDI. From the figure it is evident that robust increases are projected for all periods and scenarios examined. For the near future period, the average increase projected range from about 14 to 18 extra days/period for RCP4.5 and RCP8.5, respectively. The average increase is higher for the distant future period reaching about 21 and 46 extra days/season under RCP4.5 and RCP8.5, respectively.

Figure 6-46 Mean absolute changes in the warm spell duration index (WSDI) for the five member model sub-ensemble between the near (2031-2060) and the distant future (2071-2100) periods and the reference one (1971-2000) under both RCP scenarios (RCP4.5 and RCP8.5). In each panel M denotes the spatial average change over all the grid points covering the area with the units being the same as in the colorbar. Black dots indicate a robust change at the grid point scale while N denotes the percentage of grid points where robust changes are found

6.3.3.7 SUMMARY ON CLIMATE PROJECTIONS RESULTS

In summary, the analysis revealed robust increasing changes between both the near and the distant future compared to the reference period for the temperature related indices under both RCP scenarios. On the contrary, the changes in the precipitation related indices were found less pronounced for the near future period under both RCP4.5 and RCP8.5, while the highest and more robust decreases were identified for the distant future period under RCP8.5

6.3.4 UNSEEN APPROACH

Our ability to quantify the risk of extreme rainfall events is constrained by the limited length of the observational record. Climate models can provide a much larger sample of plausible events, providing a more realistic estimate of the risk of extremes events. The UNSEEN method (UNprecedented Simulated Extremes using ENsembles) was used to assess the risk of unprecedented rainfall events over the wine-growing regions of northern Portugal. Heavy rain in the spring can promote excessive growth of the vines and the downy mildew, both of which can require costly interventions and treatments. Heavy rainfall during late summer can reduce the grape quality and increase the difficulty of harvesting.

Observed rainfall totals over northern Portugal were calculated from gridded daily rainfall amounts in v21 of the E-OBS dataset. Rainfall amounts in E-OBS are calculated on a regular 0.1° grid (~ 12 km) via interpolation of station-derived meteorological observations. Daily rainfall totals were extracted from E-OBS for 1980-2017, which corresponds to the hindcast period of DePreSys, and were aggregated to the same spatial resolution. Rainfall totals over northern Portugal were calculated from the aggregated data for spring and summer in each year (Figure 6-46). There is no apparent trend in the rainfall totals, but considerable variation between years is evident. The highest observed rainfall total for spring (Fig. 6-46 red line) occurred in 1983, when a total of 353 mm fell. Very high rainfall amounts also fell in 1988 (336 mm), 1993 (317 mm) and 2016 (324 mm). For summer (blue line), the wettest years were 1987 (366 mm), 1993 (376 mm) and 2006 (299 mm). The year 1993 is unusual, as rainfall extremes occurred in both seasons. There appears to be fewer high rainfall extremes in both seasons from 1994.

Figure 6-47 Time series of season rainfall totals over northern Portugal from 1980 to 2017 from the E-OBS data. Data are shown for spring (April to June, red line) and summer (August to October, blue line).

Simulated daily rainfall totals were taken from the Met Office’s decadal climate prediction system DePreSys3. The model is initialised with atmospheric, oceanic, and sea-ice observational data and current anthropogenic and natural forcings, so that the simulations are representative of current real-world climate. These hindcasts were produced from 1980 to 2017, when satellite data are available for model initialisation. The hindcasts begin in November of each year, corresponding to the start of each viticultural campaign. Forty ensemble members are available for each start time, providing 1520 simulations (38 years × 40 members) of spring and late summer rainfall totals. The use of initialised climate predictions reduces model biases compared with uninitialized transient simulations of the past climate. The six- and ten-month lead times allows the forecasts from the ensemble members to diverge, producing a wide range of plausible extreme rainfall events, some of which will not have been observed. DePreSys3 is able to skilfully predict European summer rainfall. Monthly rainfall totals from DePreSys3 were summed to produce seasonal totals for spring (April to June) and summer (August to October) over northern Portugal.

The highest observed rainfall totals are 353 mm in spring and 376 mm in late summer. The observed rainfall series are reproduced in Figure 6-47 (black lines), and the highest observed rainfall totals are indicated by the horizontal dashed lines. The red lines show the rainfall totals from all 40 members of the decadal hindcasts. There are no trends in the numbers or magnitudes of the unprecedented rainfall events in the hindcasts. In each season, there is one year when the hindcast rainfall total is exceptionally high, of the order of 600 mm.

Unprecedented events occur when rainfall totals in the hindcasts exceed the highest observed totals. From Figure 6-47, the highest observed rainfall totals are exceeded in a small number of years in both seasons.

It is assumed that the unprecedented events occur with probability P , which can be estimated as the number of events divided by the sample size. A binomial approach is used to estimate the 'counting uncertainty' in these probabilities, using P as the binomial probability of success. The 95% confidence intervals in these probabilities were estimated using likelihood ratios. The probability of unprecedented rainfall in both seasons is 0.02 with a 95% confidence interval of 0.01 - 0.03. These results show that the probability of an unprecedented rainfall event over northern Portugal is low, and only one such event might be expected in the next 30-100 years.

From the observed rainfall data (Fig. 6-46), the only year when both the spring and summer were exceptionally wet during the study period (1980-2017) was 1993, when 317 mm rain fell during spring and 376 mm fell in summer. Similar events were searched for in the hindcasts, using a threshold of 300 mm for both seasons. Only nine years (out of 1520 simulations) had very high rainfall totals in spring and summer, which corresponds to a probability of ≈ 0.005 . The chance of a year similar to 1993 reoccurring in the present climate is therefore extremely low.

Figure 6-48 Unprecedented seasonal rainfall totals for spring (April to June) and summer (April to October) in northern Portugal from 1980 to 2017. The solid black lines show measured rainfall totals from E-OBS, and the dashed black lines indicate the highest observed values. The red lines represent rainfall totals from the hindcasts (40 members). Unprecedented rainfall totals are apparent when the modelled rainfall totals lie above the dashed black line in each panel.

In summary, a large ensemble of initialised climate model simulations were analysed, and the probability of unprecedented rainfall in each season was quantified. Seasonal rainfall totals considerably higher than any observed are possible in the current climate. The probability of an event in either season is low (0.02), and the chance of reoccurrence of a year similar to 1993, when both seasons were exceptionally wet, is extremely small. The results help inform the need for costly adaptation investments for vineyard management, such as better availability of spraying machinery and labour, high-gauge drainage, landslide controls or even abandonment of exposed vineyard areas.

5 7. EXPLOITATION OF RESULTS

The outcome of this work can be exploited in a number of possible future ways:

- This work includes for instance relevant material that can be included in future scientific publications already planned and in preparation;
- A new paradigm for the scientific background underpinning the climate services for the agro-food sector can be proposed based on the main scientific outcomes here reported;
- Several methods to further improve the MED-GOLD services (e.g. MED-GOLD Dashboard) by adding new contents even after the end of the project to go closer to the market in terms of new source of info (satellite) and innovative approach (UNSEEN) have been here presented;
- The main scientific contents of this work can further favourite the commercial exploitation of the MED-GOLD Services by demonstrating the scientific consistency of the information provided to users in the MED-GOLD Dashboard

Moreover, the future further development of the service can take advantage of a number of lessons learnt:

- Including in the service datasets already used and known by the users can definitely favour the usability and the trustiness of the tool. In this specific case the adoption of PTHRES dataset increased the interest of users;
- The downscaling of climate predictions towards higher resolution, even if not necessarily increases the skill of the forecast, can play a key role in favouring the adoption of the tool;
- The reconstruction of the past climate conditions, and the monitoring of current climate conditions in a near-real time environment is of particular interest for users of wine sector;
- As the most part of the indicators here taken into exam span over several months, the here presented technique of merging observations and predictions seems to be of particular interest to increase the skill of seasonal forecast.

END OF DOCUMENT

